

UNDEFEATED: SOCIAL SOCCER

AN APPROACH TO
AMATEUR FEMALE SOCCER
IN SANTA CRUZ DE LA
SIERRA - BOLIVIA

2023

Presentation

The San Isidro Center emerged in 2005, as an initiative of young people, women and men who, concerned about the lack of opportunities, crime, social stigmatization, poverty and inequalities, decided to act directly and take the public spaces to transform their reality through art, culture and sports, as tools for social transformation.

It is 2006, when the San Isidro Center breaks the anonymity and positions itself in the international context as a project that promotes sports with values, using the social Soccer methodology, which allows it to participate on its own merits in the First Street Soccer World Cup organized by FIFA (parallel to the official FIFA World Cup), obtaining 3rd place for Bolivia.

Through the methodology of social football, the San Isidro Center has worked -and continues to do so- in the promotion of human rights, gender equality and equity, inclusion and leadership, using sport strategically to address different social problems that directly affect girls, boys, adolescents and young people such as school violence, participation and insecurity, and so on, achieving excellent results.

In these years of uninterrupted work, we have carried out different systematizations and research on the history of the Andrés Ibáñez citadel, art during the pandemic in Santa Cruz, the situation of the performing arts, literary publications, in addition to having participated in different publications and studies both locally, nationally and internationally on various topics.

On this occasion, we feel happy and proud to contribute with this work on amateur women's soccer, which has valuable honest and first-hand information on the barriers and challenges faced by women soccer players -of all ages and social levels-, from Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia.

Thank you very much for your support. We'll keep going.

Introduction

Consistent with our social work and given the lack of data and information regarding access to sport, mainly about women's Soccer, we are exploring this scenario that has become more relevant in our society and globally, but still faces barriers and challenges of a cultural, political, social and economic nature.

Thanks to the Project "Undeclared: Social soccer" we were able to collect quantitative information, through the application of an online survey, with open and closed questions, resulting in the participation of 70 soccer players and the collaboration of 10 sports leaders of women's soccer amateur teams from Santa Cruz de la Sierra. In the same way, in the process of implementing the project and the different sporting events organized, talks, meetings and conversations were held with soccer players aged between 18 and 45-, who entrusted us with their concerns and proposals for the development of this sport and to guarantee the participation of women in soccer practice.

It is necessary to clarify that these data are not absolute, nor do they reflect the reality of all female soccer players. However, they provide us with a basis for identifying areas of improvement to promote positive change. The ultimate goal is to foster an inclusive and equitable environment in which women soccer players can thrive and reach their full potential.

Finally, we must mention that this research arises thanks to the support of the United States Embassy in Bolivia, and the Alumni Inspira Bolivia community through the Undeclared: Social Soccer Project, which was aimed at promoting the empowerment and inclusion of women in the soccer field, led by the San Isidro Center, in alliance with amateur women's soccer clubs.

**GENERAL
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE
AMATEUR FEMALE
SOCCER**

Age and marital status

According to the data collected, 50% are women between the ages of 25 and 45. While the other half are women between the ages of 18 and 24.

Marital Status

60 %

40 %

Single

Married or
cohabiting

80% of the soccer players were born in Santa Cruz. While 20% were born in other departments of Bolivia.

From the above, we can infer that:

- Soccer is an activity that requires time, dedication and commitment, which can make it difficult to reconcile with family and work life.
- The young population finds in sports a space of opportunities and difficulties.
- Soccer is a space for socialization and identification for single people, who find in it a sense of belonging and support.

→ Maternity and soccer

The fact that 40% of the players surveyed have children suggests that some women have managed to reconcile motherhood and their passion for football, or that they have the support of their partners, families or social networks to make their roles compatible.

Maternity

40%

60%

Mothers

Non Mothers

It could also reflect a greater diversity of profiles and personal trajectories among the players, who do not conform to a single or homogeneous model of a female soccer player.

This can be a positive sign of female empowerment and challenging gender stereotypes that traditionally limited their participation in sport after maternity.

However, it is necessary to consider the challenges that these players may face. Raising children comes with an additional load of responsibilities and obligations, which can make it difficult to dedicate time and energy to soccer.

It is very important to note that women have faced additional challenges in participating in sport compared to men. Social expectations, gender roles, and family responsibilities can affect women's participation in sporting activities, such as soccer.

Academic training of soccer players

Professional

30%

35%

University

20%

Bachelor

Certificate

10%

5%

N/R

These data allow us to reflect on the different realities and roles that amateur soccer players face in terms of their occupation and responsibilities.

Occupation of soccer players

Data on the occupation of female amateur soccer players allow us to reflect on the various realities they face and the importance of addressing the barriers that may arise due to work and family responsibilities.

From the data obtained, we can highlight

Most female soccer players have some form of occupation, whether working full-time, part-time, or combining work and study. This indicates that many players are balancing their work and sporting responsibilities, which can be challenging.

The presence of players who do housework is also significant. This highlights the persistence of traditional gender roles, where women are responsible for domestic work and, in turn, find time to participate in amateur football.

The absence of unemployed soccer players in the sample suggests that all the players have an occupation. This can be an important factor for participation in soccer, since employment can provide resources and stability that favor sports practice.

It is encouraging to see that some soccer players have their own business, which indicates an entrepreneurial spirit and economic autonomy. This can have a positive impact on their participation in soccer, as they may have more flexibility in their schedule and resources to invest in their sporting development.

Employment provides resources and stability that favor sports practice

Traditional gender roles still persist; Balance: home/sport

Entrepreneurial spirit and economic autonomy. Flexibility to play and invest in soccer

Soccer at home

These data allow us to reflect on the participation and family support towards women's soccer, as well as the importance of the domestic environment in the development and continuity of the sport.

40%

They claim to be the only ones who play soccer at home.

30%

live with less than 3 women who also play soccer.

25%

They share their hobby with more than 5 women in their house.

From the data obtained, we can highlight

The data reveals that women's soccer continues to be a minority activity and one that is not valued socially, since most of the players do not have the support or example of other women in their family environment.

There are cultural and structural barriers that make it difficult for women to access and participate in soccer, such as a lack of resources, facilities, opportunities, recognition or visibility.

It is encouraging to see that some female players come from environments where more than 5 women play soccer. This indicates a favorable and supportive environment for the practice of women's soccer, where participation in the sport is valued and encouraged.

In summary, the data on the number of women playing soccer in the home environment highlights the importance of encouraging participation and support for women's soccer in all family settings.

Experience playing soccer

45% of the players play soccer between 3 and 6 years old. This finding highlights the importance of promoting and maintaining women's interest in soccer from an early age, providing opportunities for long-term participation and development.

The presence of some players with more than 15 years of experience shows the dedication and trajectory of these players in soccer. These players can play an important role as role models for other players and contribute to the growth and visibility of women's soccer.

Reflection:

Soccer is a relatively recent practice that has gained followers: Greater recognition of women's soccer.

Women's soccer has a high dropout or turnover rate, perhaps due to the lack of institutional, economic, and media support compared to men's soccer.

Demands and social pressures that fall on women in relation to their gender role, family, work and personal life, which can hinder continuity and commitment to soccer.

Many women face difficulties and barriers to access soccer, among them: gender stereotypes and prejudices.

Women's soccer is an emerging and dynamic reality, but also vulnerable and unequal

Composition of the teams

The 10 amateur soccer leaders who participated in the following investigation indicate that the teams are made up of 10 to 15 players, which shows some heterogeneity in the composition of the teams.

But, they also point out that there is a certain instability and inconstancy of the players who have different roles and responsibilities (and needs) that do not allow them to have a certain regularity and permanence in the clubs.

Training frequency

Regarding the frequency of their training, the information collected reveals the difficulties and inequalities that women face in the field of sports,

Only 2 teams train more than once a week

4 teams do not train for time and economic reasons

4 teams don't train at all

This shows that women have fewer opportunities and resources to dedicate themselves to sport than men, due to the family, work and domestic responsibilities that fall on them, as well as the lack of institutional and social support.

Annual participation in women's soccer championships

7 out of 10 teams participate in less than 5 championships per year

1 team participates in less than 10 championships a year

2 teams participate in less than 3 championships a year

No team declares not to participate in any championship.

These results suggest that women's soccer continues to be a marginal and undervalued activity in the sports field, and that it faces multiple social, cultural, and economic barriers to its development and visibility. However, a circuit of sports tournaments has been generated that allows them to share and compete at different times of the year.

Organization of the championships

Most point out that it is the Neighborhood Councils that organize the championships, followed by another women's club or their own team. What is striking is the absence of these events organized by the Mayor's Office and/or the Government.

Neighborhood

Council another team

Your same team

Lack of resources and spaces for its development

Low presence and support of public institutions for women's sports

Protagonism of community and women's organizations in the promotion and management of women's soccer

Means of transport most used by athletes

The means of transportation used by amateur soccer players to travel to matches can be an indicator of the opportunities and barriers they face in their sport practice.

These data reveal:

The use of public transport may mean a lack of resources or difficulty in accessing other more comfortable or faster options such as taxis, private transport or motorcycles.

Public transport may mean more travel time, higher cost or exposure to situations of risk or discrimination

The use of public transport may limit the possibility of sharing the trip with colleagues or family members.

The use of public transport can limit the participation in championships due to the place of choice of place or the schedule of the matches.

As for private transport, this may mean a higher socioeconomic level or greater personal autonomy.

The use of private transport can mean greater responsibility when driving

Regarding the use of other means of transport (bicycle and/or motorcycle), it may be due to their availability and access.

Walking, it can be: proximity of the place, personal preference

Economic investment for each soccer championship

To get an idea of the current situation of amateur women's soccer, we have asked the sports leaders how much money they allocate, approximately, to each tournament in which their teams compete.

The results are the following:

Analysis

Most of the 43% teams invest between 801Bs to 1000Bs in each championship, which indicates a high level of commitment, but also an economic limitation to access more expensive resources.

The rest of the teams invest between 50Bs to 800Bs in each championship, which shows great disparity and inequality between the participating teams, as well as a lack of support and investment in amateur women's soccer by sports and public institutions.

Sports leaders have to make great efforts to cover the basic expenses of their teams, such as transportation, food, equipment, refereeing and registration. This limits the possibilities of improving the quality of amateur women's soccer, of expanding the number of players and of offering better conditions for their practice.

Sponsorship for women's Soccer

To find out about the support that amateur soccer teams receive from private companies, we found the following result: 100% of the respondents stated that they do not have any sponsorship for the purchase of sports equipment, and that they and their players are the ones who invest their own resources to cover these expenses.

The 10 clubs affirm that they do not have any sponsorship, neither from private companies nor from the public sector

Everyone buys sports equipment

Reflections

Women's soccer faces great challenges and obstacles to its development and consolidation. One of them is the lack of economic support from private companies, which limits the possibilities of accessing quality sports equipment, participating in national and international tournaments, and having adequate infrastructure for training.

Another aspect that hinders the development of amateur women's soccer is the lack of recognition and diffusion, since it does not receive the same media attention as men's soccer. This implies less visibility and social appreciation of the work and effort of the players, as well as a lower possibility of generating income from advertising or box office.

These data reveal the precarious situation of amateur women's soccer in Santa Cruz de la Sierra and the enormous gap that exists with men's soccer, which does have sponsors, the media, and greater attention and social recognition. Likewise, they demonstrate the commitment and passion of the women who practice this sport, who, despite the difficulties, continue with their dream of playing soccer.

The image is a composite graphic. The top portion shows a dark, jagged mountain range against a light sky. Below this, a soccer ball is visible, with its white panels and black pentagons. A large, vibrant green brushstroke shape is overlaid on the left and bottom portions of the image. The title text is centered within this green area.

**ACCESS, AVAILABILITY,
CONDITIONS AND NEEDS OF
SOCCER FIELDS**

Access to public courts by women

One of the main problems affecting women's soccer is the difficulty in accessing public soccer fields (administered by the Mayor's Office or the Governor's Office) where women can train and compete.

According to the data collected, 70% of the soccer players and leaders affirm that it is very difficult to find a public field to play on, while 30% say that it is not complicated.

Reasons for this situation include:

Lack of investment and public support, may be due to lack of awareness and understanding of opportunities for women and men by the authorities.

The lack of availability of schedules, the preference for men's teams, the charging of high fees, the poor quality of the facilities and the insecurity in the areas where the courts are located.

Lack of public pitches can limit the opportunities for women's development and participation in sport, as well as the lack of visibility and recognition of women's soccer.

These factors limit the opportunities and the right of women to enjoy soccer as a form of leisure, recreation and expression.

Number of public courts

From a gender and equality perspective, the fact that most of the players consider that Santa Cruz de la Sierra has few public sports fields to practice soccer is worrying.

In this regard, we have the following information and analysis.

70% consider that they do not have public soccer fields

70% of the players and leaders consider that the city does not have enough public fields to play soccer. This may indicate that there is a lack of public investment in sports infrastructure that especially affects women, who have fewer options and resources to access private spaces. In addition, it may reflect a certain discrimination or exclusion of women in the use of existing pitches, which may reproduce stereotypes or prejudices about the role and ability of women in football.

30% consider that they do have public soccer fields

On the other hand, 30% indicate that the city has many public sports fields, which may suggest that there is greater awareness and appreciation of the public spaces available by these players, who perhaps have managed to overcome some difficulties or limitations to practice this sport. It can also imply that there is a greater diversity and quality of public pitches in some areas or neighborhoods that favor the access and participation of women in soccer.

The data reveals that there is a majority perception (70%) of scarcity or insufficiency of public sports fields to practice soccer by women in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, which may be an indicator of inequality and gender discrimination in the field of sports, since women have fewer options and resources to access private or alternative spaces.

Conditions of public courts

The data corresponds to the question: What does a field need within the green area so that you can meet and play soccer? The analysis of these data reveals some interesting questions about the conditions and demands of women who practice amateur soccer in the urban context. The answers were the following:

NEED

IDENTIFIED PROBLEMS

Security and lightning

There is a perception of vulnerability and risk when carrying out this activity in public spaces, mainly at night.

This may be related to gender violence, street harassment or the discrimination suffered by women in these spaces by male users, especially.

There is a shortage or poor distribution of these resources in the green area, and that women have difficulties accessing them or reserving them in advance.

Safety and accessibility maintenance

There is difficulty in accessing public courts, it denotes the lack of public policies for the promotion of women's sports.

Existence of cultural or economic barriers that limit their participation.

Current facilities do not meet the minimum hygiene, privacy and comfort requirements for women. This may reflect a lack of sensitivity or interest on the part of the authorities or managers of sports venues towards the specific needs of women.

Services public and transportation

Women value the proximity and ease of getting to the court, whether for reasons of time, cost or safety.

In conclusion, it is essential to guarantee safe, accessible and adequate conditions, as well as to promote an inclusive and respectful culture in the sports environment. This implies considering the specific needs of women and girls, and ensuring their participation in decision-making related to sports venues. This implies considering the specific needs of women and girls, and ensuring their participation in decision-making related to sports venues.

COMMUNICATION AND DIFFUSION

Dissemination and promotion of amateur women's soccer

Most of the leaders use informal and personal means, such as social networks, direct invitations or WhatsApp groups, to publicize the event and attract players. These means are limited in scope and depend on the interest and motivation of the leaders and players themselves.

60% know digital sites for the promotion and dissemination of women's soccer (women's soccer, futbolconnect, others), compared to 40% who only use their own Social Media.

On the contrary, there is no mention of formal and collective media, such as universities or companies, which could contribute to greater visibility and legitimization of amateur women's soccer.

In general terms, we can affirm the following:

The lack of visibility by the traditional media makes it difficult to recognize and appreciate it. This problem is mainly due to the fact that women's soccer does not generate economic benefits or commercial interest.

However, given this absence and support from the traditional medias, there are other spaces and opportunities for women's soccer to grow.

Communication and Calls for championships

It is interesting to note that, in all cases, the 70 players and the 10 managers actively and frequently use different forms of communication to contact and summon each other when there is a championship.

These forms of communication include WhatsApp groups, email, social networks like Facebook, Instagram and TikTok, as well as phone calls.

This equality of access and use of different communication channels is a positive indicator in terms of gender equality in soccer, since the players have the same opportunity to receive information and participate in the championships, regardless of their gender.

Adaptation to new forms of communication and integration with digital platforms

M.C. They fulfill different functions and objectives, including expression and identity, mobilization, organization and participation.

M.C. They contribute to creating and strengthening a culture and a community, based on solidarity, respect and equality.

This equality of participation and access to different communication channels demonstrates an active participation and a modern mentality among the players and managers, taking advantage of the technological tools available to keep in touch and coordinate their sports activities.

COVID-19 AND SOCCER

COVID-19 and Soccer

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on sports practice around the world, particularly affecting women and girls, who have faced additional barriers to sport participation due to the pandemic.

Among the problems identified within the framework of the Invictas Project, we have:

Identified problems

Frustration and interruption of the sports routine of the players

Players were forced to abandon or reduce their sports activity due to the lack of spaces, resources and support for their practice.

Players lost contact and cohesion with their teammates, who are a source of support, identity and belonging.

Players assumed a greater burden of domestic work and care.

The lack of social interaction and the inability to train and play together may have created a feeling of disconnection and isolation.

Players suffered a deterioration in their physical and mental health due to confinement, stress and uncertainty.

Affectation on the general well-being and motivation to participate in sports activities.

MOTIVATIONS TO HAVE A TEAM AND PLAY TO SOCCER

Motivations to play soccer

From the testimonies, we can interpret that the affective factor is a source of motivation to join a women's soccer team, conceived as a space for socialization and building affective ties between women, as well as an expression of identity motivated by personal or collective challenges of participating in championships.

The sport as a human right

Soccer is an activity that should be within the reach of all people, regardless of their gender, age, origin or social status. Soccer is seen as a form of expression, participation and demand for women's human rights.

I'm a fan of the team in which I play

Sense of belonging and identification with the soccer team to which they belong. Soccer is a passion that is shared with other colleagues, with the fans and with the community. Soccer is a way of living and feeling.

Sport: Socialization and friendship

Soccer is an opportunity to share experiences, to support each other and to have fun together. Soccer is a way of relating and taking care of yourself.

professional possibility

They reflect the dream and aspiration of many girls who want to dedicate themselves to soccer professionally. Soccer is a way to grow and progress.

Welfare and health

Sport gives them the opportunity to exercise, improve their physical condition and promote a healthy and active lifestyle.

Scholarship opportunity or job

Soccer as a means to access educational and employment opportunities that improve their quality of life. Soccer is a tool that allows them to combine study with work, or access scholarships or financial aid. Soccer is a way of learning and working.

soccer as fun

The pleasure and enjoyment that playing soccer produces. Soccer is an activity that amuses them, entertains them and makes them feel good. Soccer is a way of playing and doing sport.

→ Motivations to have a soccer team

The testimonials of the women's soccer team leaders reveal a diversity of motivations and interests to practice this sport, ranging from the affective factor to the competitive factor, including the inclusive factor and the passionate factor.

"Family and friends"
(Leader 1)

"Include new sports engineers"
(Leader 2)

"I've been playing soccer since I was a girl, then I quit. After a long time I dared to team up for a championship, then the players started arriving and we became good friends and I continued teaming up with the same girls. Because I feel good making her play and we share beautiful moments"
(Leader 4)

"To have a better quality of life and spend fun time with friends"
(Leader 7)

"Passion for soccer"
(Leader 8)

" Well, I've been playing sports since I was 12 years old, and being in the team where I am right now, for me it's not just a team, it's a family to which when I play with them I feel the satisfaction and pleasure of playing the sport, it's the best, even if it's loyal to them."
(Leader 5)

"Because sport is for everyone and for everyone. It is a human right, but it is also a game that allows us to develop"
(Leader 10)

"The possibility of changing the situation of sport so that women have more possibilities and access"
(Leader 9)

"Since the age of 8 I have practiced futsal and soccer, but years ago there were not as many championships as today. Starting in 2010, I formed the current team with a group of friends"
(Leader 6)

"In the neighborhood, I started with a group of friends, first for fun, then with a view to wanting to win an award and thus put the team more seriously"
(Leader 3)

DIFFICULTIES AND PROBLEMS THAT SOCCER PLAYERS GO THROUGH

Main difficulties and problems that women go through when playing soccer

According to the data obtained, we can highlight the main difficulties and problems that women face when they want to play soccer.

These issues highlight the challenges women face in the context of soccer, and it is important to address them from a gender perspective to promote equal opportunities and inclusion in sport.

It affects the safety and well-being of the players, creating a hostile environment and limiting their full participation in the sport.

Many women are unaware of the existence of women's soccer teams, which can decrease opportunities to participate in the sport.

Gender stereotypes can discourage women from playing soccer, either due to fear of rejection or a lack of female role models in the sport.

Lack of fields close to their location, which implies greater logistical challenges and limitations on participation.

Gender stereotypes, generates: lack of understanding, lack of emotional support or lack of logistical support for their participation in soccer.

Main difficulties and problems that women go through when playing soccer

Gender inequalities rooted in the unequal distribution of work and care burden, which limits the time and availability of women to participate in sport.

This can manifest itself in the lack of resources, lack of development opportunities in the field of Soccer.

Lack of sponsorship, lack of financial resources or lack of employment opportunities related to Soccer.

This can affect the gaming experience and the creation of an inclusive and collaborative environment.

The costs associated with participating in sport (team registration, clothing, and transportation) may be unaffordable for some women due to precarious financial situations.

These problems show that Soccer continues to be a space socially constructed as masculine, where women have difficulties to access, stay and develop. Likewise, they reflect that women who play soccer must face a double burden of roles and social expectations that require them to reconcile their sporting passion with their family or work obligations.

Main difficulties and problems that women go through when playing soccer

There is not one to leave the children with

Caregiving responsibilities may fall disproportionately on women and the lack of childcare options affects their ability to fully participate in sport.

Gender violence and maleness

This includes sexist attitudes, discrimination and gender stereotypes that create barriers to women's access and participation in sport.

maleness and discrimination

Discriminatory attitudes and behaviors can manifest themselves in the form of unfair treatment, lack of institutional support and social barriers to the participation of women in Soccer.

invisibility of women's soccer

Women who play soccer suffer from invisibility and media, institutional and social devaluation that reduces their opportunities and prestige

lack of infrastructure

The lack of accessible and safe sports facilities limits opportunities for practice and competition.

In summary, these difficulties reflect the gender inequalities and structural obstacles that still persist in the field of Soccer, and highlight the need to take measures to promote gender equality, create inclusive environments and overcome these barriers to the full enjoyment and participation of women in sport.

SOCIETY SEXISM AND DISCRIMINATION

→ society and maleness

From a gender and equality perspective, the data provided by amateur soccer players suggests that there are still barriers and challenges for women to exercise their rights in sport, as we will see below.

Regarding the fact that if ever the players and leaders of amateur women's soccer were victims of machismo for playing soccer or promoting it, 90% affirmed that they were, compared to 10% who indicated the opposite.

MALENESS SOCIETY IDENTIFIED FACTORS

Lack of visibility and recognition of women in Soccer

Lack of resources and support for the development of women's soccer

Persistence of stereotypes and prejudices about the role of women in sport

Discrimination and harassment that women who practice sports considered "masculine" may suffer.

These factors can generate inequalities, exclusions and barriers to the access and permanence of women in sport, as well as affect their self-esteem, motivation and satisfaction.

On the other hand, 10% do not consider that our society is sexist or that it prevents them from exercising their rights as athletes.

NON SEXIST SOCIETY IDENTIFIED FACTORS

- Players have had positive experiences in the sport, such as having the support of their families, coaches or teammates.
- They have access to adequate facilities and materials.
- They receive fair and respectful treatment, or feel valued and recognized for their performance and skills.

These factors can favor the inclusion, integration and participation of women in sport, as well as improve their well-being, confidence and enjoyment.

→ In conclusion, the data reflect the diversity of opinions and experiences of amateur soccer players about society and machismo. However, it is important to recognize and address these inequalities in order to promote gender equality in sports.

Society and discrimination

When asked if they had ever felt discriminated against or belittled by their friends, colleagues or family for playing soccer, the data revealed the following:

80% experienced some type of discrimination or contempt for playing soccer, which shows the persistence of gender stereotypes and prejudices rooted in society that question the legitimacy (disapproval or exclusion of soccer players) and the value of women in this sport, since they associate soccer with men.

In addition, they stated that they constantly experience this discrimination or contempt, which shows a persistence of discriminatory attitudes in their immediate social environment.

30% of the players indicated that they have ever felt discriminated against or belittled for playing soccer.

On the contrary, only 20% of the players stated that they had never felt discriminated against, which could indicate greater social acceptance (more inclusive and respectful environments that encourage female participation in this sport) or greater personal resistance to macho attitudes.

Soccer has historically been a masculinized and exclusive space for women, who have had to face numerous barriers and stereotypes to access and participate in it. In this sense, sport can be understood as a social practice that reflects and reproduces the structures, values and norms of the society in which it develops.

Thus, sport is not only a physical activity, but also a form of expression, communication and identity. In essence, it has also been an area of resistance and empowerment for women who have claimed their right to practice sport in conditions of equity and respect.

PROPOSALS FOR AMATEUR FEMALE SOCCER

Proposals for the promotion and development of women's soccer

Below, we collect the contributions and proposals of leaders and soccer players regarding the opportunities and challenges facing amateur women's soccer and how it can be developed and promoted with the aim of building a fairer society with equal conditions through sport.

What does it take for women's soccer to amateur develops and spreads?

Media outreach and collaboration

Promote greater media coverage of the events and achievements of women's soccer, as well as establish strategic alliances to promote visibility and interest in the sport.

Leadership and empowerment

Workshops and courses that promote leadership and female empowerment in the context of Soccer (development of leadership skills, decision-making, active participation in leadership and management roles).

Permanent education

Workshops and sports training courses for women, which address technical, tactical and physical development aspects (improvement of skills and performance, strengthening of their confidence and knowledge)

Permanent District Events

Promote the regular organization of women's sports events in the districts (it will facilitate participation and access to women's Soccer, and will foster an inclusive and grassroots sports culture).

Investment in infrastructure

It is essential to invest in the construction and maintenance of public fields (available and accessible) for the practice of women's soccer with adequate and safe facilities.

Proposals for the promotion and development of women's soccer

What does it take for women's soccer to amateur develops and spreads?

Coordination and planning between amateur clubs

Establish coordination and planning mechanisms that promote collaboration and synergy (it will allow sharing resources, organizing championships and providing opportunities for soccer players in a broader environment).

systematize and share experiences

It is important to systematize and share experiences and good practices in women's soccer (collect and disseminate information on successful programs, management models and strategies that can serve as a reference and guide).

does not discriminate and stereotypes of genre

Challenge and overcome gender stereotypes that limit the participation of women in Soccer (work on education and awareness to promote equal opportunities, discrimination and the prevention of violence in society and in sport).

Support of the family

Family support is crucial for the development of women's soccer (family values and supports the participation of women in the sport (in terms of dedicated time, resources and emotionally)).

championships university students

Encourage the organization of women's soccer championships (it will promote participation and competition). These events provide opportunities for development and growth in an educational and formative environment.

Resources for championships

Adequate economic resources to organize and support women's soccer championships and competitions (cover logistics, infrastructure, prizes, and promotion of these events).

conclusions

Sport is a social phenomenon that reflects and reproduces the structures, patterns and organizations of society. In this sense, sport is crossed by gender inequalities that exist in the social, cultural, economic and political fields.

Soccer is a social phenomenon that reflects and reproduces the power relations, values and norms of the cultures and subcultures that practice it. It is essential to work towards creating inclusive and supportive environments, where all women and girls have the opportunity to participate in Soccer, regardless of their home environment.

Working towards gender equality in Soccer means ensuring that all players, regardless of their place of birth, have equal opportunities to develop their skills and fully participate in the sport.

It is essential to encourage and support the participation of women in Soccer in all settings, including the home environment. This implies educating and sensitizing families about the importance and benefits of women's soccer, as well as providing opportunities for participation and development at the local and community level, regardless of their marital status, place of origin, level of training, etc.

Working towards gender equality in Soccer implies guaranteeing the equitable availability of public spaces for the practice of Soccer, which will contribute to promoting and strengthening the participation and development of female Soccer in the city.

Similarly, it is essential to promote a culture of respect and safety on the courts, promoting rules and policies that prohibit any form of discrimination or gender violence. This includes addressing and preventing sexual harassment and bullying of any kind, and ensuring that players feel safe and secure in the sporting environment.

In summary:

- **It is essential to combat gender-based violence and promote gender equality in all aspects of Soccer to create a safe and equitable environment.**
- **It is essential to promote policies and services that facilitate child care and allow women to spend time playing Soccer without additional worries.**
- **Economic inequality can limit women's access to sport and it is important to work on the creation of financial support programs and scholarships to guarantee equal opportunities.**
- **It is important to foster values of camaraderie, respect and solidarity between the players and the teams.**
- **It is necessary to promote alliances between companies and women's sports to promote equal opportunities and the sustainable development of women's soccer.**
- **It is critical to advocate for policies and programs that promote gender equality and provide a favorable environment for women's participation in sport.**
- **Building understanding and support from families is essential to promoting equal opportunities in sport.**

INQUIRY PROCESS TEAM.

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